

CORRELATIONS OF DAMAGE MECHANISMS AND MATERIAL MICRO-STRUCTURE IN TENSILE LOADED HOOP STRUCTURES

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1 General Introduction

Composite materials are anisotropic and heterogeneous with highly variable microstructures. The ultimate failure of composite laminates is generally determined after a series of interacting events, such as matrix cracking and fibre failures, occurring on a microscopic level. These microscopic processes need to be understood to determine their effect on macroscopic strength. Existing models and theories to predict composite failure either rely on overly simplified failure criteria [1, 2] or are based on idealised assumptions of the material structure [3,4].

Voids are a common microstructural feature in composite materials, particularly when non-autoclave manufacturing processes are used, resulting either from entrapped air during the manufacturing process or from volatiles arising from the resin during the cure stage [5]. Studies have attempted to determine the effect of these voids on composite mechanical properties, for example [5, 6, 7]. Such studies show that void content is detrimental to a variety of material properties including: interlaminar shear strength, longitudinal and transverse modulus and flexural strength, longitudinal and transverse tensile strength and modulus, compressive strength and modulus, and fatigue resistance. Analysis methods have been predominantly limited to two dimensions, however in more recent years CT has been used to characterise the meso-structure of composites including void segmentation in 3D [8, 9]. Quantitative micromechanical analyses are largely lacking however, particularly in terms of failure initiation processes, where both the experimental tools to capture failure within bulk material at high resolutions has been largely absent to date.

In this current study multi-scale computed tomography techniques have been used to obtain

three-dimensional data of the internal material structure and damage mechanisms in loaded hoop structures to provide an unprecedented understanding of the material behaviour under load.

This characterisation is key to enabling correlations between all relevant damage mechanisms and the material structure to be identified, which will determine the relative influence of material and microstructural features on performance; something which until now has not been possible. This research is particularly focussed on the effects of voids and fibre breaks, including a modified tessellation approach to void-fibre break correlation mapping.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

Hybrid composite hoop structures were manufactured via filament winding and cured out of autoclave, including voids within the composite layers. The experimental structures consisted of an internal aluminium liner, filament wound with carbon/epoxy (CFRP) and glass/epoxy (GFRP). The outer diameter of the structures were approximately 90mm, with a total wall thickness of ~4.15mm. The approximate thickness of each material layer is shown in Fig. 1. The circumferential layers were wound at ~90° to the axis of the structure and the longitudinal layers at ~20°.

The samples were pressurised to near failure. Acoustic Emission (AE) sensors were used as an aid to locate damage spatially and temporally without seeking to distinguish the damage mechanisms from the AE data itself. This work was carried out in continuation of a study by Kalantzis [10]; involving multiple hoop structures taken to failure whilst acoustic emissions were recorded. The previous

work Kalantzis [10] has shown that final failure sites can be located by peaks in the AE signal amplitude and energy.

Six AE sensors were applied to each test structure, the structures were then internally pressurised at a rate of 0.5MPa per second, using a Top Industrie S.A. Banc Hydraulique 2000bar testing press. The AE signals were used to determine the regions of highest damage for further analysis via high resolution CT. The acoustic emission signal amplitude, energy and counts were recorded for each sensor. An event was located when at least four sensors detected an emission, on the basis of the time of arrival at each sensor and the speed of sound in the composite walls. The signals were pre-amplified by 40dB and band-pass filtered outside the range of 100kHz to 1MHz to remove the background noise. The AE signals were recorded and analysed with a Vallen AMSY 4 data acquisition system.

The analysis has been carried out for the CFRP component of the samples only. The CFRP provides the majority of the strength and stiffness of the structure.

Fig. 1: Schematic section illustrating the material layup.

2.1 Multi-scale Computed Tomography

Micro-focus CT (μ CT) has been used to provide images at moderate to low resolutions, shown in (a) and (b), from whole component samples and sectioned sub-regions. In addition imaging using the European Synchrotron Research Facilities (ESRF), enabled micron scale resolutions of critical regions of interest, shown in (c), providing structural information down to single fibre levels.

μ CT images were taken using an X Tek Benchtop 160Xi scanner at the University of Southampton, providing resolutions of $\sim 75\mu\text{m}$ and $\sim 15\mu\text{m}$ for the macro and meso scale imaging. In this system X-rays are generated when an accelerated electron beam collides with a metal target (molybdenum or tungsten). A focal spot size down to $\sim 3\mu\text{m}$ is achievable in this system. Due to the conical beam of the μ CT, a smaller sized sample will achieve higher resolution. As such the finest

resolution (i.e. $\sim 3\mu\text{m}$) is achievable for a field of view of 3.6mm cross-section, with the largest possible objects ($\sim 90\text{mm}$ cross-section) yielding a voxel resolution of about $75\mu\text{m}$.

The SRCT setup at ID19 of the ESRF, was used to obtain a resolution of $1.4\mu\text{m}$ (although higher resolutions are achievable). In comparison to the μ CT, X-rays are generated from very high energy electrons circulating in an accelerator and associated interactions with an undulator device in this case. The high beam flux enables relatively short exposure times, with satisfactory imaging results being obtained for scans in the order of 5-10 minutes. The coherent beam enables an edge detection method to be exploited via near-field Fresnel diffraction [11], to assist in the detection of small features such as voids, cracks and fibre breaks.

Multi-scale imaging was carried out as follows:

1. Macro-scale imaging of the whole structure diameter using the μ CT at a resolution of $\sim 75\mu\text{m}$.

2. Meso-scale imaging of small Regions of Interest (ROI) extracted from the whole structure at the locations of highest energy and amplitude of the AE signals, and scanned at a resolution of ~ 20 to $8\mu\text{m}$ (dependant on sample size). The ROIs were extracted by first cutting short hoop sections ($\sim 20\text{mm}$ wide) and imaging at $\sim 20\mu\text{m}$. The hoop sections were then mounted in epoxy resin (to constrain and prevent the release of residual stresses and corresponding delamination of the structure) and smaller rectangular sections of $\sim 20 \times 20\text{mm}$ were cut using a slow speed diamond saw, enabling scan resolutions of $\sim 8\mu\text{m}$.

3. Micro-scale imaging of sub-regions extracted from the meso-structure samples above. A slow speed diamond saw was again used to cut narrow "matchstick" coupons, which were then metallographically polished to $\sim 2 \times 2\text{mm}$ in cross-section and $\sim 20\text{mm}$ length. Figure 2 shows schematically the $2 \times 2\text{mm}$ cross-section area of the CFRP samples, with the 20mm length corresponding to the axis of the structure. These matchsticks were imaged using SRCT at a resolution of $1.4\mu\text{m}$.

The software packages VG Studio Max 2.1TM and ImageJTM were used to analyse the reconstructed CT images to determine the internal material characteristics and highlight particular features of interest.

Fig. 2: Multi-scale CT imaging approach of a hybrid composite/metallic structure: (a) and (b) μ CT scans of whole structure and sub-region. (c) SRCT image of plies and local fibre distribution.

3 Voids

3.1 Void segmentation

The macro-scale image shown in Fig. 3 shows a three dimensional image of the structure, in which the voids have been segmented and shown in black via a grayscale threshold. It shows varying regions of voids with distinct regions running parallel to the longitudinally wound fibres (20°). The macro-scale images show larger features can be distinguished (i.e. at approximately $75\mu\text{m}$ length scales and above) and thus show only larger voids.

In order to segment all fine scale void populations accurately the high-resolution SRCT images were used, in which each individual void is clearly identifiable, as shown in Fig. 4.

A trainable segmentation tool [12] in the image processing package Fiji™ was used to segment the voids within sub-volumes of the circumferential plies ($\sim 1800 \times 160 \times 450 \mu\text{m}$). In this process approximate areas of voids and background microstructure (the fibres and resin) are first selected manually. The plugin is then trained on the examples given, and automatically segments the rest of the image. A set of features of the example regions are created by individually applying various filters (for example, Gaussian blur, Mean, Minimum and Maximum), and a classification tree is then built linking the features from the image to the features from the examples. The plugin then uses the features

from the examples to designate the class of the feature of interest (i.e. voids or background).

3.2 Tessellation

Once the voids had been segmented, a 3D "finite body" tessellation was carried out to determine the spatial distributions of the voids in relation to other features; for example damage mechanisms. Boselli et al. [13] particularly show the relevance of this form of tessellation to analysis of irregular and anisotropic bodies, where simpler Dirichlet tessellation of centroids leads to physically unrealistic representation of the surrounding space.

The segmented binary voids, shown in Fig. 5a) were labelled such that each void was associated with its own identifying number. The tessellation technique uses a Euclidean 3D distance transform using the MATLAB function from Mishchenko [14].

The distance transform was computed from the edge of voids as opposed to individual centroids: a number is assigned at each pixel in the image corresponding to the distance between that pixel and the nearest edge of a void. Fig. 5c) shows a 2D slice from the resultant 3D distance transform of the voids from Fig. 5a).

A 3D "watershed" was then calculated for 26-connected pixels, i.e. 26 neighbouring pixels connected at the face, edge and corners using the

Fernand Meyer algorithm [15]. This creates cells separated by a watershed line, as shown in Fig. 5d).

The border cells were then removed, as the cells found at the border of the image being analysed may be influenced by voids outside the field of view. The border cells inline with the fibre direction are kept, as typically the voids are long and run through the majority of the length of the image. Fig. 5e) shows the remaining cells and corresponding voids used for analysis. It should be noted that in the figure some of the cells appear as though they contain more than one void, however they are in fact one void that adjoin further into the sample volume.

Fig. 3: Macro-scale slice of the cylindrical section showing geometry of voids.

Fig. 4: SRCT high resolution image of composite.

Fig. 5: a) 3D view of segmented voids, b) 2D slice of voids, c) 2D slice from 3D distance transform d) watershed of distance transform e) 2D slice of the remaining cells and corresponding voids after the border voids have been removed.

Fig. 6: Micro-scale SRCT image of matrix cracks in the longitudinal layer of the CFRP.

4 Damage Mechanisms

The macro-scale analysis shows only larger delaminations and voids (Fig. 3). Other fine scale damage, such as matrix cracks, requires higher resolution imaging, and thus smaller samples. The high-resolution SRCT images allow matrix damage to be identified at a much higher resolution. Fig. 6 shows multiple matrix cracks in the longitudinal layer intersecting with voids. Fig. 7 shows a 3D volume in which all the cracks in the longitudinal layer and the corresponding voids with which they intersect have been segmented. The composite has been digitally removed to reveal the damage in three dimensions. It is clear that each of the matrix cracks (in light grey) intersect with at least one of the voids (in dark grey). The complex structure of the cracks and voids emphasise the importance of 3D analysis.

It is possible to identify clearly individual fibre breaks located in the circumferential layers, shown in Fig. 8. No fibre breaks were found in the longitudinal layer; the circumferential layers in this structure carry the majority of the stress when loaded (being the stiffest composite layer in the circumferential direction) and thus the fibre breaks found within this layer are the dominant damage mechanism. The fibre breaks were manually counted from SRCT images within the circumferential ply sub-volumes for the near failed samples.

Fig. 7: 3D SRCT image of cracks intersecting with voids

Fig. 8: Micro-scale SRCT image of fibre breaks in the inner CFRP circumferential layer.

5 Material structure and damage mechanisms correlations

The resultant tessellation enables highly localised measurements, such as cell and void areas, C_A and V_A , local void volume fraction V_f (V_A/C_A), cell and void geometry and centroids. It enables correlations to be determined between fibre break densities with void volume fractions, void dimensions and spatial distributions, to determine any affects the voids may have on fibre break numbers and locations.

Fig. 9 shows the fibre break density versus void volume fraction for each tessellated cell for a sub-volume within the CFRP from which the fibre breaks were quantified. It shows there is no distinct correlation between the fibre break density and the volume of the voids. Fig. 10 shows the fibre break density versus void dimensions, for which the x and y coordinates correspond to the transverse directions and the z coordinate the fibre axis (the limits of the z axis according to the sample volume is marked on the graph). This figure again shows no first order correlation between the void size and fibre break density.

The distance transform map was then used to determine the distances of all the fibre breaks to their nearest void in the sub-volume. The histogram of the nearest neighbouring fibre break distance of each void is shown in Fig. 11. The results are compared to a random distribution of fibre breaks, where the average of 10 random distributions is

shown on the graph. The random fibre breaks are determined using a uniformly distributed random function to place the same number of fibre breaks observed in the sample. The randomly distributed fibres took into account the real material structure, in that they were not placed within locations of voids or where a previous fibre breaks had been placed.

Fig. 11 shows there is a distinct peak in the number of fibre breaks occurring at a distance of less than 2.5 pixels (corresponding to half the fibre diameter) from the edge of the voids. 16.25% of all the fibre breaks were found to occur within half a fibre diameter of a void, compared to 5.75% for the random distribution. This strongly suggests that voids influence fracture in the immediately surrounding fibres. The remaining data can be seen to follow a similar pattern to the random distributions, with a peak in fibre breaks occurring at a distance between 10 and 15 pixels from the closest void location.

Whilst void proximity clearly influences fibre breaks, it is unclear from this study to what extent the correlation of fibre breaks with voids affects the overall onset of specimen failure. Initial models have been developed to correlate structural behaviour with fibre break processes (e.g. [16]), however the incorporation of voids and non-idealities were not included. The incorporation and validation against experimental results reported here remains subject to on going work.

Fig. 9: Fibre break density versus void volume fraction for each tessellated cell

6 Conclusions

High resolution computed tomography has been demonstrated as a very powerful tool to characterise microstructures in composite materials, and to correlate the occurrence of damage with microstructural features in three dimensions. In the present work the locations of cracks and fibre breaks were correlated with voids.

A high level of confidence can be placed in the results as the features are viewed directly at the relevant length scale. Voids were segmented in three dimensions to analyse the spatial distribution and determine any correlation with damage mechanisms. It was shown in three dimensions that matrix cracks intersect with the voids. The correlation with fibre breaks was less distinct. There was no first order correlation found between fibre break density and void volume fraction or void dimension. It was evident however that there is a correlation between fibre break locations and voids, with 2.8 times more fibre breaks occurring within half a fibre diameter of voids than estimated for a uniform random distribution of the same number of breaks.

The experimental approach demonstrated in this work, is most powerful when combined with models for the material response, allowing the concept of “data rich mechanics” as a tool to inform material and process development to become a reality.

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Fig. 10: Fibre break density versus void dimensions in the transverse and axial (in line with the fibres) directions

Fig. 11: Histogram of distance of fibre break to nearest neighbouring void